

LANGUAGE USED BY INDIVIDUALS WITH CONFIDENCE PROBLEMS PATTERNS AND NARRATORY IDENTITY THEORY

MEHMET FATIH HANOGLU

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Abstract

In this study; It has focused on how these narratives – the way they express themselves – affect their language skills, especially in individuals who express themselves with and without self-confidence both in writing and verbally. Depending on, this effect, how there is a difference as a narrative identity between individuals who express themselves as self-confident and insecure and how these individuals use these story forms.

It has been studied what the effect of language skills is in creating in the formation of identity, narrative theorists; tried to reveal that self-stories, main narratives, lived events shape identity. According to this theory; individuals tell all the variables about their identities by narrating them through narratives. It has also been demonstrated by many studies in the literature that there is a link between the impressibility of an anxiety or fear and its inability to express it. In this study, first, individuals who express themselves as self-confident and insecure were identified with their own expressions. In the research, it was found that the variables in language patterns are related to self-confidence and as the main hypothesis, people with self-confidence It is found that they use different language patterns from insecure people and that these patterns are internalized, and it is understood and negative by the audience.

Keywords: *Identity, Language Patterns, Self-Confidence, Narrative Identity*

Introduction

Throughout history, thinkers have discussed the relationship between language, thought, emotion and behavior. Wittgenstein's "The limits of our language are the

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limits of our world." The word is one of the propositions that many linguists argue today. The statement of John Langshaw Austin, Professor of Philosophy of Language at Oxford University, "The speaker does not describe things, he does something." In

fact, it is a proposition stating that speaking is not just talking. (1955) The first narrative theories in the modern sense, starting from the 20th century; They pointed out that individuals tend to express their past by telling stories and those individuals form an identity by living according to this story form.

Pasupathi is one of the pioneers who built a bridge between narrative identity and conversations. (2001) With this bridge, a new understanding has been started to be compiled in studies by different disciplines, from psychology to sociology, from linguistics to anthropology. Narrative studies have attracted the attention of disciplines such as history, anthropology, folklore, psychology, sociolinguistics, communication studies and sociology, especially since the 1960s, and has become an interdisciplinary field of study (Riessman & Quinney, 2005).

Schiffrin (1996) in his work titled *Narrative As Self Portrait: Sociolinguistic Constructions of Identity* draws attention to the fact that narrative ability creates a resource for revealing self and identity both locally and globally. In her study of the narratives of American Jewish women about problems in their families, she found that linguistic analyzes of the stories revealed the characteristics of the constructive and epistemic selves of the narrators, and the social dynamics in their families (solidarity, autonomy, power, and social identities as mothers).¹

According to the identity functions model, active construction of identity involves engaging in various cognitive activities about who the individual is; Passive structuring of identity, on the other hand, refers to more orientation towards identification and imitation of who the individual is. (Adams & Marshall, 1996) Narrative studies and concepts function as a strong predictor of one's mental health as the sum of the themes and meanings that a person derives from his own life. (Schwartz et al., 2015) Narratives focus on individual differences as well as the sameness and uniqueness of the individual. These differences are tried to be determined by various methods (McLean & Syed, 2017).

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In this study, in which we examined the issue of self-confidence, which is one of these personal differences, a road map was created by focusing on the language in the narrative identity. Using language in an individual sense is a subjective behavior. Choosing words, using them with linguistic structures that we see fit, is related to our linguistic competence, but it is a subjective situation revealed by our linguistic performance.

Many research methods for narrative identity have also been developed. (McAdams, 2011; cited in Schwartz et al., 2015). These approaches, identity; It claims that it consists of thoughts reflecting the life story of the person, the ability to integrate this life story in a coherent way, and the ability to make inferences from both positive and negative life events (Schwartz et al., 2015). In this respect, narrative identity is a subjective interpretation of the personal past, which adds integrity to life and includes both positive and negative life events (McLean & Syed, 2017).

In this study, by examining self-confidence, identity, and active and passive structuring of identity; It examines the connection between what is said and what is not told in the language patterns used by individuals who express themselves positively or negatively regarding self-confidence. Life Story and Linguistic Subjectivity: Sociolinguistic Indicators' Life Story and Linguistic Subjectivity: Sociolinguistic Implications / Meryem İen S.3

2 Life Story and Linguistic Subjectivity: Sociolinguistic Indicators Life Story and Linguistic Subjectivity: Sociolinguistic Implications / Meryem İen S.

CONFIDENCE

Turkish Language Institution self-confidence concept; 'Self-reliance', that is, explained as the feeling of self-confidence. (self-confidence)

A person with high self-confidence is a person who accepts the conditions that he cannot change, shows the courage to change the conditions that he can change, and has the wisdom to distinguish between the conditions he can change and the ones he cannot change.

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It is peaceful, happy and makes those around it happy. (Soner, 2000).

Confidence; It is the individual's feeling of well-being because of developing good, positive feelings towards himself. In short, we can say that self-confidence is an individual's belief in himself.

Lack of self-confidence; It can be defined with concepts such as self-doubt, passivity, submission, over-adaptability, loneliness, sensitivity to criticism, insecurity and feeling unloved.

Self-confidence begins to be gained at an early age. Low self-confidence can be defined as negative attitude, poor judgment and insufficient critical thinking skills, dependent relationships, being anxious and depressed in new situations to adapt to. High self-confidence is cheerful outlook, good judgment and critical thinking skills, healthy relationships, and easy adaptation to new situations.⁴

IDENTITY

Eric Ericson thought of identity as a kind of harmony. Human identity is formed by a sense of subjectivity and is a personal integrity. In the most general sense, it is the individual's developing commitment to various aspects of the self to define and make sense of himself. The more positions an individual occupies in society, the more diverse selves he has. At this point, the concept of identity accompanies the self. In other words, the individual creates an identity for each position he occupies in society.¹

Identities are the meanings that an individual creates as the owner of a role or as an individual. In other words, the meaning of being a mother or a teacher for the individual constitutes the content of their identity.

¹ Taking Life Against* Tolgahan Topuz; Prof. Dr. Bengi Semerci

Self-perception, on the other hand, is the whole of a person's perceptions about himself, which begins to form from the age of two with the influence of birth and the environment and can be shaped positively or negatively.

In the Schiraldi self-esteem scale, the following 12 judgments are graded between 0 and 10, with 10 points being correct.

I am a respectable person.

I am as valuable as anyone else.

I have the necessary qualifications to live well. When I look at myself in the mirror, I feel good.
I am not a failure.

I can laugh at myself and make fun of myself. I am happy to be myself.

It is not necessary for me to be accepted by others to love myself.

I love myself in all circumstances and I stand by myself. I am satisfied with the way I have developed myself.

I respect myself.

It is more important to me to be myself than to be someone else.

METHOD

In this study, first, individuals who express themselves as insecure and individuals who express themselves as self-confident –to form a participant group- were determined by means of a questionnaire. Permission was obtained from the NGOs where the survey was conducted. To increase the data reliability in the tests to be made later in the study,

the participants were also asked about their education levels; They were asked to score 1(one) "I am very insecure", 7(seven) "I have full self-confidence". This survey; 20 adult women, 20 adult men, who said "I am very insecure", made with 1000 people between the ages of 20 and

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50; 20 adult women and 20 adult men who said “I have full self-confidence” were selected because they had the same education, close socio-cultural and economic levels. There are many different definitions of the concept of self-confidence. Instead of starting from these definitions, first of all, what the participants gave to the surveys; The study started by accepting the answers of “(1) I am very insecure” or “(7) I have full self-confidence” as correct, and then a self-confidence test was also conducted with the participants, and the accuracy of the statements was tested a second time, with limited accuracy.

FIRST SURVEY SAMPLE:

NAME-SURNAME (OPTIONAL) :

YOUR EDUCATIONAL LEVEL :

YOUR AGE :

YOUR AVERAGE MONTHLY INCOME: TEL NO (OPTIONAL) :

1 (ONE) I AM VERY CONFIDENT –

****Please rate yourself from 1 to 7:*

7 (Seven) MY CONFIDENCE IS FULL

I Accept the Use of This Information in Scientific Studies.

Your Information will not be used for any other purpose by the KVKK Rules.

SIGNATURE

It was observed that 22% of the 1000 participants who filled the first questionnaire did not fill in their Name and Surname, and 37% did not fill in their phone number. Those who do not fill in all the requested information; It was observed that they gave an average of 3 points to the instruction "Please grade yourself between 1 and 7".

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A total of 80 participants, 20 women and 20 men, 40 people who expressed themselves as “very insecure” and 20 women and 20 men 40 people who expressed themselves as “very self-confident”, were contacted again by obtaining their Kvkk and study participation permissions. In this communication, the participants were first asked to take a self-confidence test online.

CHICKS

1* Never

2* rarely 3* Usually 4* often 5* always

QUESTIONS

1. I see myself as a successful person.
2. I can control my excitement around others.
3. I am not dependent on others for my choices.
4. I can cope with difficulties in life.
5. There is no insurmountable problem for me.
6. I respect the opinions of others.

I believe that I can overcome my problems.

8. I do not hesitate to participate in social activities.

I stand behind the decisions I make.

10. I believe that I can be self-sufficient.
11. I am an active person.
12. I can be self-critical.

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13. I can ask other people questions about things that I do not understand.
14. I adapt to new environments.
15. I am a person at peace with myself.
16. I will defend my right to the end when necessary. 17. I can struggle to get what I want.
18. I can express myself comfortably.
19. I accept myself and others as they are. 20. There are enough people around me that I can trust.
21. I do not hesitate to take responsibility.
22. I can sympathize with other people's criticism.
23. I try to think positively even in times of trouble. 24. I am not afraid to stand out.
25. When I fail, I do not give up right away.
26. I can easily communicate with other people.
27. I am a valuable person.
28. I can make friends easily.
29. I am not afraid of others when expressing my thoughts.
30. I can make easy decisions.
31. I am a social person.
32. I love myself.
33. I deserve the praise of other people.

Then, the participants were asked to fill in the sentence completion form below.

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SENTENCE COMPLETION FORM

1. People.....
2. My family
3. My close friends... 4.
- My current relationships.....
5. Most of the people in my close circle.....
6. Boys/girls about me.....
7. My relations with the other sex.....
8. According to others, I am
9. When in a group.....
10. When you are alone
11. When I compare myself with others.....
12. It worries me the most.
13. When I experience a negative situation, I blame
14. I am
15. I have difficulty speaking to people or situations.

After the test and the participants were given preliminary and final information about the process, each participant was given an equal amount of time (5 minutes), and they were asked to verbally answer the question "Can you tell us about yourself?" on the phone.

Opening questions were asked when there were occlusions in the speech.

It was shared with the participants that all the words they said would be translated into text using a program in which voice recordings would not be taken in the speeches,

Speeches were converted into text using the "Voiser" program.

EXAMPLE: 1(One) I AM VERY CONFIDENTIAL GROUP

-Can you tell us about yourself?

... how can I express myself.... ..

I am doing.....

-How do you see yourself?

... Physically...B usually.... A

I was born in X Place,Y job

It was observed that the insecure group hesitated a lot while expressing themselves and needed additional questions. It has also been observed that they use more residual sounds such as "iii" and "eee."

EXAMPLE: 2 (Seven) SELF-CONFIDENCE FULL GROUP

-Can you tell us about yourself?

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I usually express myself as X, I do job Y, I live in Z, I have hobbies D,

It has been observed that the self-confident group can continue to express themselves if they hear the audience's answers such as "huh" and "yes".

Care was taken to ask questions with the same tone of voice in order not to affect the participants. The results of whether the questioner was male, or female was not evaluated in the study.

It has been observed that there are many different variables by looking at the

language patterns from the number of words used by the participants while expressing themselves. The information received was evaluated epistemologically with the clustering method.

1. GROUP: 20 WOMEN WHO SAID I AM TOO SECURE

2. GROUP: 20 MEN WHO SAID I AM TOO SECURE GROUP 3: 20 WOMEN WHO SAY I HAVE FULL CONFIDENCE GROUP 4: 20 MEN WHO SAY I HAVE FULL CONFIDENCE

In this evaluation, the number of words in the Voiser voice/word recordings and the meanings of the words were examined.

In this study, intonation and emphasis were not taken into consideration.

WORD NUMBERS

1. GROUP: 20 WOMEN WHO SAID I AM VERY UNSAFE 255 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

2. GROUP: 20 MEN WHO SAID I AM VERY UNSAFE, AVERAGE 234 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

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3. GROUP : 20 WOMEN WHO SAY I HAVE FULL CONFIDENCE, AVERAGE 545 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

GROUP 4: 20 MEN WHO SAY I HAVE FULL CONFIDENCE AVERAGE 562 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

NUMBER OF POSITIVE WORDS (Example: I Won; I Did...)

1. GROUP: 20 WOMEN WHO SAID I AM VERY UNSAFE 26 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

2. GROUP: 20 MEN WHO SAID I AM VERY UNSAFE 38 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES AVERAGE

3. GROUP : 20 WOMEN WHO SAY I HAVE FULL CONFIDENCE 76 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

GROUP 4: 20 MEN WHO SAY I HAVE FULL CONFIDENCE 88 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES AVERAGE

NUMBER OF NEGATIVE WORDS (Example: I Won, I

Could not...)

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1. GROUP: 20 WOMEN WHO SAID I AM VERY UNSAFE 43 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

2. GROUP: 20 MEN WHO SAID I AM VERY UNSAFE 37 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES AVERAGE

3. GROUP : 20 WOMEN WHO SAY I HAVE FULL CONFIDENCE, AVERAGE 8 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

GROUP 4: 20 MEN WHO SAY I HAVE FULL CONFIDENCE

AVERAGE 7 WORDS IN 5 MINUTES

The words that have been recorded by dividing into the above groups and their meanings are not mentioned; It continues in the form of words such as name, place name, family information, adjectives. Therefore, they were not considered. When we look at the audio/word recordings, we had to use much more words when communicating with the groups in the 1st and 2nd groups who said to themselves "I am very insecure". The data obtained from the audio recordings were shown to 10 people with the same education level, in written and mixed form, without giving any further information, on the condition that the names and surnames of the people are kept confidential, and the question was asked orally: "50% of the owners of these articles say that they are "very insecure". .

Which ones do you think you can separate?İ

It was revealed that the participants were able to understand an average of 36 very insecure group members from the written text. Another study could not be conducted regarding the separation of the participants from the self-confident group members -due to the lack of data-

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Familiar words among the 1st and 2nd group participants who said “I am very insecure”

has been found.

- Very Much
- Did it happen
- Maybe
- Can I
- I do not know
- I wish
- Tired
- How?
- Is it finished?

The ability to express meanings related to negative life events is seen as a key theme in the investigation of narrative identity. (Waterman, 2015b).

It was also observed that the participants who said they were insecure were stressed about the question as if they were in an exam.

Familiar words in the 3rd and 4th group participants who said “I have full self-confidence”

has been found.

- I am ready
- My preference
- Different
- Path
- Of course

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- Success
- Energy/k
- Strong
- Impact

The ability to complete life stories with narratives develops during adolescence and emerging adulthood. Studies in emerging adulthood emphasize individual differences in narratives (McLean & Syed, 2017).

LIMITATIONS:

- 1- The data in this study is limited to only 80 people. In addition, help was received from 10 people only to be a source for another research.
- 2- Self-confidence approaches in the study are limited to the qualities measured by the scales used.
- 3- Findings that emerged because of the study; It is limited to the data obtained from the data collection tools to be used in the research.
- 4- The study has not been compared with other research methods.

CONCLUSION

The language patterns used by individuals who have self-confidence problems in the study . different from self-confident individuals, from the perspective of narrative identity theory, insecure individuals have different narratives both in writing and verbally, they especially use clear words and concepts very little, even individuals who only read these words can recognize the owners of words and their relationship with self-confidence, by looking at language

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patterns, It has been revealed that individuals with a lack of self-confidence have a desire to speak more indirectly and briefly.

It has also been observed that self-confident individuals speak more clearly and understandably and use more words than insecure individuals.

It is suggested that experiments should be conducted on individuals with low self-confidence by restructuring their language patterns / using the words used by self-confident individuals.

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